

Matrix form of notation for mass ratios in chemical compounds (stoichiometry) as applied to X-ray spectral analysis

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Summary

When solving the equations of X-ray spectral analysis in order to determine the composition of the substance, it is often necessary to take into account the restrictions in the form of mass ratios in chemical compounds (stoichiometry) for the complexes of elements included in the analyzed sample [1, 2].

The article proposes a mathematical matrix entry of stoichiometric relations for an arbitrary chemical formula. This allows you to simply formulate the problem of solving the equations of spectral analysis as a vector problem of estimating parameters in the presence of such restrictions.

Model

We propose that we have a sample consisting of complexes such as oxides, silicates, sulphides and so on with known stoichiometric formulas, for example, a metal alloy $(Al_2O_3)_x(MnO)_{1-x}$ where x is not known. Our goal is to obtain ratios of concentrations that do not contain an unknown index.

We will rewrite this chemical formula for further calculations in the form $(Al_2O_3)_{x_1}(MnO)_{x_2}$. The weight concentrations of the elements in this sample can be expressed by the indices of the chemical formula as the ratio of the molar weight of the constituent elements to the molar weight of the

entire sample, that is, $c_1 = c_{Al} = \frac{2xM_{Al}}{M_{alloy}}$, $c_2 = c_{Mn} = \frac{(1-x)M_{Mn}}{M_{alloy}}$, $c_3 = c_O = \frac{3M_Ox + M_O(1-x)}{M_{alloy}}$

where M_{Al}, M_{Mn}, M_O the atomic weights of aluminium, magnesium, and oxygen,

$M_{alloy} = (2M_{Al} + 3M_O)x_1 + (M_{Mn} + M_O)x_2$ are the molar mass of the alloy. If there are no contaminations in the alloy, then $x_1 + x_2 = 1$.

These relationships can be rewritten in matrix form using the algebra of non-square matrices [1]. Let be $M_1 = M_{Al}$, $M_2 = M_{Mn}$, $M_3 = M_O$ the atomic weights of the corresponding elements. If $\mathbf{c}$ is the vector of weight concentrations of elements, the index $\mathbf{x}$ is the vector of indices of the complexes included in the compound, $\mathbf{Q}$ is the matrix of converting of indices in concentration, then in our case

$$\mathbf{c} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\frac{M_1}{M_{alloy}}, & 0 \\ 0, & \frac{M_2}{M_{alloy}} \\ \frac{3M_3}{M_{alloy}}, & \frac{M_3}{M_{alloy}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\frac{M_1}{M_{alloy}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{M_2}{M_{alloy}} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{3M_3}{M_{alloy}} & \frac{M_3}{M_{alloy}} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Further $\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \end{bmatrix}$, then $c_3 = \mathbf{B} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \end{bmatrix}$ or $\frac{3}{2} \frac{c_1}{M_1} + \frac{c_2}{M_2} - \frac{c_3}{M_3} = 0$, these are concentration dependences, where chemical indices and molar mass of the alloy are no longer present.

If in matrix form, then $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{c} = 0$, where $\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 1 & -1 \\ 2M_1 & M_2 & M_3 \end{bmatrix}$ is the matrix - string.

The number of rows in the matrix $\mathbf{G}$ is equal to the difference between the number of elements included in the stoichiometry equation and the number of indices.

The proposed recording method is easily generalized to a more complex multicomponent sample using non-square matrices.

Let there be a sample containing n elements with weight concentrations $[c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n]$ that are related by stoichiometric ratios. Then the vector of weight concentrations and the vector of chemical indices are connected by the matrix equation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_1 \\ \mathbf{c}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x} \quad (2)$$

Where $\mathbf{c}_1, \mathbf{c}_2$, an arbitrary partition of the vector $\mathbf{c}$ into two components, and $\mathbf{A}$ и $\mathbf{B}$ two correspondingly selected matrices in the division of the common matrix $\mathbf{Q}$, as described above.

Using one of these matrices, the vector $\mathbf{x}$ is expressed in terms of a part of the vector $\mathbf{c}$. Since the second part of the vector $\mathbf{c}$ is also expressed through the vector $\mathbf{x}$, by substituting the vector $\mathbf{x}$, binding of vector components is obtained due to presence of stoichiometry of the sample.

If the dimension of the vector $\mathbf{c}_1$ is less or equal to the dimension of the vector $\mathbf{x}$, then $\mathbf{A}$ is a non-square matrix, and

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{A}^+ \mathbf{c}_1 \quad (3)$$

For details of designations and definitions, see [3]. Since $\mathbf{c}_2 = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}$ then

$$\mathbf{c}_2 = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^+ \mathbf{c}_1 \quad (4)$$

Or $\mathbf{c}_2 - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^+ \mathbf{c}_1 = \mathbf{0}$. Finally

$$\mathbf{G}\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (5)$$

where the matrix $\mathbf{G} = [\mathbf{I}, -\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^+]$

As in the above example $x_1 + x_2 = 1$, then $c_1 + c_2 + c_3 = 1$ is automatically valid.

But that's not always the case. If there are elements in the multicomponent sample that are not part of the stoichiometric formula, then we must take this into account. Let now $\mathbf{c}_m$ be the fraction of the part of the concentration vector that is included in the stoichiometric formula and $\mathbf{c}_{n-m}$ the fraction of elements that are not included in it. We'll get it instead of (5) $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{c}_m = \mathbf{0}$. In addition, the sum of all

analyzed concentrations is one, $\sum_1^n c_i = 1$. Then the complete equations of a priori constraints

$$\mathbf{G}_{p \times m} \mathbf{c}_m + \mathbf{0}_{p \times (n-m)} \mathbf{c}_{n-m} = \mathbf{0}_p$$

$$\mathbf{1}'_m \mathbf{c}_m + \mathbf{1}'_{n-m} \mathbf{c}_{n-m} = 1$$

Or compact

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G}_{p \times m} & \mathbf{0}'_{p \times (n-m)} \\ \mathbf{1}'_m & \mathbf{1}'_{n-m} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_m \\ \mathbf{c}_{n-m} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_p \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Here $\mathbf{G}_{p \times m}$ is the matrix of stoichiometric ratios, $\mathbf{1}'$ unit vector, $\mathbf{0}$ zero vector.

If the concentrations are found, then the vector of indices based on (1) is then

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{Q}^+ \mathbf{c}_m = \mathbf{Q}'(\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{Q}')^{-1} \mathbf{c}_m \quad (7)$$

We may need the following result:

Let

$$M_{Al_2O_3} = 2M_{Al} + 0M_{Mn} + 3M_O,$$

$$M_{MnO} = 0M_{Al} + 1M_{Mn} + 1M_O,$$

$$M_{alloy} = (2M_{Al} + 3M_O)x_1 + (M_{Mn} + M_O)x_2 \text{ are the molar mass of the alloy.}$$

$$\text{Then } c_{Al_2O_3} = x \frac{M_{Al_2O_3}}{M_{alloy}} = x \frac{2M_{Al} + 0M_{Mn} + 3M_O}{M_{alloy}} = 2c_{Al} + 0c_{Mn} + 3c_O$$

$$c_{MnO} = (1-x) \frac{M_{MnO}}{M_{alloy}} = (1-x) \frac{0M_{Al} + 1M_{Mn} + 1M_{O}}{M_{alloy}} = 0c_{Al} + 1c_{Mn} + 1c_{O}$$

If we denote $\mathbf{C}' = [C_1 \quad C_2] = [c_{Al_2O_3} \quad c_{MnO}]$ the vector of oxide concentrations, then

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

That is, in general, if the sample is presented as a collection of complex compounds, oxides, sulfides or any other, then $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{c}$ and

$$C_i = \sum a_{ij} c_j, \quad (9)$$

the weight content of the compound is a linear function of the concentrations of elements.

Conclusion

Interestingly, the algebra of such non-square matrices is used with success in chemistry to balance chemical reactions. The algebra language records the fact that the number of atoms on the left side of the chemical reaction should be equal the number of atoms on the right after the reaction. A balance of the masses of these atoms or chemical compounds consisting of them is also recorded. In non-equilibrium reactions, the yield of the reaction products is described by the concentration vector, that is, by the vector in question.

This formulation turned the chemistry of kinetic reactions into a mathematical discipline with very interesting and rapidly developing mathematical applications. This is relevant in the chemistry of reactions of gas mixtures, nuclear reactions, biochemistry [4, 5].

Similar to the balance of masses (concentrations of elements), the balance of electric charge and other similar, known a priori equations of balance, are formulated.

The given results allow to combine mathematical description of quantitative spectral analysis, which is mentioned here at the beginning, and mathematical description of chemical formulas [5]. This opens up future prospects for the application of dynamic remote spectral analysis in the control of kinetic chemical reactions.

Literature

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